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Project Newsletter

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All INAIR Project Results Are Now Available

The INAIR project has completed its activities and made available an integrated set of free tools and resources designed to address AI-related skills gaps among micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) in the European retail sector.

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INAIR at the OECD: Exploring the Future of Retail

On 12 June 2026, the INAIR consortium participated in the foresight workshop AI and the Futures of Retail at the OECD headquarters in Paris. The workshop explored the forces, technologies and trends that could shape the retail sector up to 2040.

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Policy Recommendations for the Retail Sector

The consortium has published the policy paper *Recommendations for Equitable and Sustainable AI Adoption in European Retail SMEs*, providing evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, education and training institutions, industry representatives and organisations supporting retail SMEs.

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ALL INAIR PROJECT RESULTS ARE NOW AVAILABLE

OUR KEY OUTPUTS

The INAIR project was established to support European retail MSMEs in understanding and adopting artificial intelligence effectively, responsibly and sustainably. Over its 30-month implementation period, the consortium developed an integrated, multilingual learning ecosystem addressing the sector's digital and AI-related skills needs. **Today, all the project's main results are publicly available.**

 AI Skills Needs and Gaps Research: The project began with a transnational analysis conducted in Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Poland and Romania. Through desk research, statistical analysis, labour-market analysis and engagement with industry experts, the consortium identified the technical, transversal, organisational and digital competences required for responsible AI adoption in retail.

 AI Core Curriculum: Building on the research findings, the consortium developed an educational programme structured around 16 learning blocks and three proficiency levels. The curriculum covers AI fundamentals, data-driven decision-making and practical retail applications, together with digital mindset, trustworthy AI, organisational change and sustainability.

 AI Skills Assessment Tool: The AI Skills Assessment Tool is designed to guide users through a personalised learning journey. It begins with a short questionnaire in which users provide information about their organisational role, professional function, prior familiarity with AI and organisational context. Based on these inputs and the results of an initial assessment, the tool identifies the user's current level of knowledge and recommends the most relevant learning pathway.

 Open Educational Resources: The curriculum was translated into 16 interactive and modular Open Educational Resources. The resources include retail examples, scenarios, knowledge checks, guided reflection, self-assessment activities and multimedia content. They are available in English, German, Greek, Italian, Polish and Romanian.

 E-Learning Environment: The project results are integrated into a multilingual digital learning environment through which retail workers and business owners can follow a personalised and self-paced learning pathway. Users can complete an initial assessment, access their assigned learning modules, monitor their progress, complete a final assessment and obtain a certificate when the applicable completion requirements are met.

Start learning at your own pace and explore AI resources designed around actual retail needs.

SIGN UP

PILOT RESULTS

The integrated programme was piloted in the consortium countries between March and April 2026. The pilot assessed the relevance, usability and perceived learning value of the platform, educational resources and assessment approach.

- 242 users participated in the pilot, of whom 178 completed the initial assessment;
- feedback was collected from 75 retail-sector participants and 61 external experts;
- 88% of end-user respondents reported that the programme improved their understanding of AI in retail;
- 85% reported increased confidence in considering or adopting AI solutions;
- 72% stated that they intended to integrate AI-based tools or approaches into their work;
- 84% rated the overall quality of the programme positively.

The results indicate that the programme was perceived as relevant and useful by both retail participants and external experts. They also highlight the importance of combining accessible training with practical examples, personalised pathways and guidance on responsible implementation.

In addition to providing learning resources directly to retail workers and business owners, INAIR placed particular emphasis on supporting trainers, education providers and intermediary organisations. To facilitate the use of the programme in face-to-face, online, blended and organisational training settings, the consortium published the **Practical Guide for Facilitators**.

The digital toolkit includes:

- **User Manual:** step-by-step guidance on navigating the INAIR environment, supporting learners and managing learning activities;
- **Use Case Collection:** practical scenarios illustrating how the resources can be used in contexts such as staff onboarding, upskilling and reskilling;
- **Content Library:** a searchable collection of complementary materials, articles, videos and practical examples concerning AI in retail;
- **Explainer Videos:** accessible video guidance introducing the structure of the programme and the use of its resources.

Explore the Practical Guide and discover tools, resources and real-world examples to support AI training in retail.

[DISCOVER THE TOOLKIT](#)

INAIR AT THE OECD: EXPLORING THE FUTURE OF RETAIL

A FORESIGHT WORKSHOP IN PARIS

On 12 June 2026, we had the privilege of participating in the foresight workshop **AI and the Future of Retail** at the headquarters of the **Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development** in Paris.

The workshop brought together representatives and experts from the OECD, European Commission, retail organisations, business-support bodies, research organisations and other actors within the European retail ecosystem. Participants examined the forces already reshaping retail and considered how emerging technologies, new business models and evolving consumer behaviour could influence the sector up to 2040. The discussion also explored the implications of these changes for skills, employment, competitiveness, SME participation and public policy.

INAIR contributed insights from its research, curriculum development and pilot activities, particularly regarding the conditions that enable retail MSMEs to move from general awareness of AI to informed and responsible adoption.

The workshop provided an opportunity to place the project's findings within a wider European and international policy discussion and to contribute evidence that will inform future OECD analysis on the retail sector. The consortium will continue to share the lessons emerging from this dialogue through its policy, dissemination and post-project exploitation activities.

POLICY PAPER: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EQUITABLE AND SUSTAINABLE AI ADOPTION

The INAIR consortium has published the policy paper *Recommendations for Equitable and Sustainable AI Adoption in European Retail SMEs*. The document synthesises the project's research and implementation experience and provides evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, education and training institutions, industry stakeholders and organisations supporting retail SMEs.

Although AI offers opportunities to improve operational efficiency, inventory management, customer engagement and decision-making, adoption among smaller retailers remains uneven.

The project identified **four main groups of barriers**:

- **Skills gaps:** limited operational, strategic and managerial capacity to assess and implement AI;
- **Infrastructure limitations:** insufficient digital infrastructure, fragmented data and data-quality constraints;
- **Organisational and financial barriers:** limited capacity to manage change and uncertainty concerning costs, benefits and return on investment;
- **Trust and governance:** difficulties interpreting and applying requirements concerning data protection, accountability, transparency and the EU AI regulatory framework.

The paper argues that AI adoption should be approached as an organisational transformation rather than solely as a technology-acquisition decision.

Its recommendations include:

- **Accessible upskilling pathways:** modular, role-specific and practice-oriented training;
- **Leadership and organisational support:** management-readiness assessment, advisory services and change-management support;
- **Trustworthy AI implementation:** accessible and sector-specific guidance on responsible and compliant use;
- **Sustainable support mechanisms:** integrated funding and assistance combining training, consultancy, organisational development and infrastructure.

The policy paper is available for consultation and download through the project's open-access channels.

[DOWNLOAD](#)

WHAT'S NEXT: JOIN THE AI REVOLUTION

Although the project's formal lifecycle has come to an end, INAIR's impact is just beginning. Artificial Intelligence is rapidly transforming the retail industry, creating unprecedented opportunities to improve operational efficiency and customer engagement. **All results, resources, and the e-learning platform will remain accessible and free to all retail MSMEs.**

Join our community, share your experiences, and become a leader in digital transformation in your industry!

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